

SCHOOL FACTORS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

School factors are issues that can cause changes in strategic management, which could be internal or external to an organization. This study explored the school factors and academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State.

Descriptive research design of survey types was used for the study. The population of this study comprises all the principals and teachers in private secondary schools in Ondo State. The study sample size of 168 respondents was used. Questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. Research questions were answered descriptively while, hypotheses were tested with Multiple Regression and Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

Result revealed that there was a significant influence of the management factors on the academic performance of students. It also revealed that there was a significant relationship between school facilities and academic performance of students ($r_{cal}=0.085; p<0.05$) Based on the findings, the study concluded that to ensure high student's academic performance in any educational institution, effective management factors is required. Therefore, the study recommends that private schools in Ondo State should endeavour to upgrade the management factors in schools for improving the students' academic performance.

Introduction

Education is noted to be an effective instrument par excellence for affecting national and global development irrespective of the economic sector. Education is an important industry for social, political and economic development and is being affected by the environment within which it exists (Adediran *et al*, 2015). There is therefore no better investment a nation could make than that in education, this is why one should not remain indifferent to the lapses on the educational system (Michael 2019). Secondary education is the education given in

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an educational institution given to students after their primary school's level either public or private secondary school. A public secondary school is a school owned and controlled and financed by the government, while a private secondary school on the other hand, is a school established and controlled either by individual or private organization. Such schools are mainly financed with students' school fees. However, secondary education plays an important role in producing best quality graduates who will become great leaders and manpower for the country thus responsible for the country's economic and social development. Hence, secondary school academic performance is mostly considered as the gateway for improvement of other sectors of the education system.

Academic performance is an evaluation of the level of achievement made in process of imparting knowledge. It is a measure of intellectual excellence. Academic performance shows the level of educational attainment of an individual. It differentiates one with high knowledge content from the other with low and less competency in academic performance. According to Babatunde (2015), academic performance is the behaviours exhibited by an individual (student) which is noticeable after undergoing a in a secondary school or a school. Students' academic performance is the final grade which students get after a systematic and comprehensive measurement and evaluation of the individual student in a school setting for the purpose of making decision or judgment on his/her cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains (Ahmodu *et al*, 2018).

Management can be seen as the process or structure through which the school managers such as principles, vice principals and classroom teachers can effectively plan, direct, control and manage the available school resources in order to enable the students perform well academically (Kemenanabo, 2019). The issue of management at the secondary school level is very vital for effective teaching-learning and improvement of academic performance among students. According to Okumbe, (2001) in Kemenanabo, (2019), educational management in secondary schools (either private or public) involves the application of management principles in designing, developing and effecting resources towards achievement of educational goals. The government of Nigeria has put in place a guideline for the establishment of private secondary schools and has continually monitored the activities of secondary school owner with a view to ensure compliance with the set standard and the guidelines. Also, Government has put different policies for both private and public secondary schools in place to make education accessible, improve transition, quality, completion and retention rates to all her citizens.

School factors are those internal and external issues or factors that can influence the performance and growth of an organization or institution. School factors are issues that can cause changes in strategic management, which could be internal or external to an organization (Meibrer, 2016). School factors, according to Nghonoli, (2017) include unequal distribution of school working staff, both teaching and non-teaching, poor planning, organizing, and controlling by school management influence students' academic performance. Academic performance of students can be influenced by several management factors. However, several studies have examined management factors and academic performance in various areas but in this study, school factors would be measured as school facilities, staff motivation, and school *administration*.

School facilities refer to as those facilities that are necessary for the school to operate or exist at all such as the school buildings, classrooms, library, laboratories, toilet facilities, offices and other materials and infrastructures that would likely motivate students towards learning. A school cannot operate meaningfully without the availability of school facilities. According to Ikegbusi *et al*, (2022), school facilities is one of the yardsticks for measuring the level of educational growth and development. School facilities constitute the major components that enable the teacher to do the work of teaching very well and helping the learners learn effectively. School facilities in this study refer to the school library and school laboratories.

Library is an essential factor in teaching-learning process, it forms one of the most important educational services. Akpomi and Raji (2022) identified a school library as an instructional resource which may significantly influence pupils' achievement after controlling for pupils' family background. The importance of library has been demonstrated by the government when she expressed in the school libraries have positive impact on student achievement and thus, school library provides a quiet, well-lit study place and environment that is conducive to mental concentration. Similarly, the laboratory facilities make teaching and learning especially science students more concrete and stimulating and hence for better students' academic performance in secondary schools. The adequacy of laboratory facilities had a significant effect on the students' academic performance in Chemistry. Staff motivation is another important school factors which could affect students' performance academically. According to Safiullah, (2015), motivation is an index of inner feeling in a certain way to the need of the individual that jobs must be designed to further employee's performance and fulfillment. Consequently, motivation of teachers is essential as it affects the students directly. In the context of this study, private secondary school staff motivation is measured by payment of good salary and recognition. Oluwalola (2023) noted that Prompt payment of salaries and timely motivational packages will only motivate the teachers to give their all and bring about balanced learning and better academic performance on the part of the students. This is buttressed by Abdullahi and Babagana, (2015) that except for salary and benefits, all other components of reward introduce uncertainty. Ikonne, and Fajonyomi, (2019) opined that motivation is what drives individuals towards realizing a set goal. Thus, if an organization or institution such as the private school wants its employees to act or perform in a certain way to enable them achieve the school's mandate; it has to have an understanding of the kind of motivation that will encourage the employees to perform in the desired manner. The kind of motivation such as salary and recognition.

Moreover, school administration is vital to the academic performance of private secondary schools. Effective administration in school has been widely noted as a factor that will make a difference between achievers and non-achievers. According to Olaniyan (2021), the primary aim of school management has to do with the improvement of teaching, learning, and all other activities in school. It is the administration of the education system in which a group combines human and material resources to supervise, plan, and implement strategic and operational structures to execute an education system. The school administration in this study is considered under the quality of human resources (teacher qualification), and instructional supervision. Among those things that help an educational institution to achieve its objectives are human resources. School human resources include teaching and non-teaching staff. However, the students' performance in a particular school (either public or private) depends on the type of teachers the school has, their experience, professional qualifications, and their commitment to work. Nghonoli, (2017) findings reveal that qualifications of teachers and their ability to perform well in the classroom are key factors in improving the quality of education.

Instructional supervision is the systematic analysis of information during implementation of a program to ensure that employees follow the laid down principles, policies and procedures in executing a given task (Kanyip 2022), A principal as an instructional administrator is responsible for maintaining and improving the quality of instructional for effective and efficient attainment of the set objectives of a school. Also. Kanyip,(2022) described the principal as an instructional administrator and he or she is responsible for maintaining and improving the quality of instructional programs for effective and efficient attainment of the set objectives of a school. Instructional supervision is therefore any program which helps teachers achieve both qualitative and quantitative instructional delivery. In the school system, instructional supervision is concerned with using methods, principles and practices of various techniques to establish, develop and execute the goals, policies, plans and procedures

necessary to achieve educational goals. The principal is thus faced with the responsibility of supervising teachers generally to improve their instructional performance. This study therefore, investigated the influence of some management factors on the academic performance of students in private secondary school in Akure, Ondo State.

Statement of the Problem

Academic achievement is the main goal of a school's existence. To achieve this goal in Nigeria secondary education, there is need for increased academic performance of students in the secondary school system both public and private schools. At every level of education, the students are expected to be provided with the factors that would encourage them in their studies. This is because any little discouragement would contribute to the students' lack of interest in their academic pursuit. The researcher observed that the major contributors to academic performance of students of private secondary school have been the issue of school factors such as school facilities, administration skills, and staff motivation. Through the researcher's investigation, it is quite pertinent that unavailability of these factors affects the smooth running of the private secondary school and this cannot bring about improvement in students' academic performance. The researcher therefore, sought to research on the relationship between the school factors and students' academic performance in private secondary school in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated the school factors and academic performance of students in private secondary schools in Ondo State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Ascertain the level of school facility in private secondary school in Ondo State.
- ii. determine the relationship between staff motivation and academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State
- iii. determine the relationship between the school administration and academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State
- iv. Examine the level of the academic performance in private secondary school in Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following questions were developed to guide the study:

- i. What is the level of available facilities in private secondary school in Ondo State?
- ii. What is the level of motivation in private secondary school in Ondo State?
- iii. What is the level of school administration in private secondary school in Ondo State?
- iv. What is the students' academic performance in private secondary school in Ondo State?

Research Hypothesis

One hypothesis was developed to guide the study:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between school factors and academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State

Methodology

The descriptive research design of Survey types was used for the study. The population of this study comprised all the principals and teachers in private secondary schools in Ondo State. The sample size for this study was one hundred and sixty-eight (168) respondents including the principals and the teachers using simple random sampling. Self-developed questionnaire and a Proforma was used as instruments for data collection. The questionnaire was titled "School Factors Questionnaire (SFQ)" and The Student Academic Performance Proforma (SAPP). The research questions were answered using frequency distribution, percentage and mean; while hypothesis one was tested with multiple regression, 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of available facilities in private secondary school in Ondo State?

Table 1: The level of available facilities in private secondary school in Ondo State

S/N	School Facilities	SA %	A%	D %	SD%	Mean	Decision
1	Library facilities provides a conducive environment for reading, and researching, thus, improving students' performance.	32 26.2	48 39.3	25 20.5	17 13.9	2.98	Moderate
2	Library search systems makes library interesting to use for assignment purposes thus, improving students' academic performance	51 41.8	25 20.5	32 26.2	14 11.5	2.94	Moderate
3	The availability of school library helps teachers to prepare for lessons	48 39.3	32 26.2	17 13.9	25 20.5	2.89	Moderate
4	Other physical facilities such as toilet, playground, eatery, among others make school environment lively and interesting for both students and teachers	32 26.2	25 20.5	51 41.8	14 11.5	2.83	Moderate
5	Students' academic performance becomes heighten when they are taught with appropriate laboratory facilities	51 41.8	32 26.2	14 11.5	25 20.5	2.76	Moderate
6	Laboratory facilities enable students understand the scientific interaction around them thereby improving their retention	32 26.2	48 39.3	17 13.9	25 20.5	2.66	Moderate
7	Availability of clean blackboards or whiteboards aids students note taking and memorization for better academic performance	48 39.3	32 26.2	17 13.9	25 20.5	2.89	Moderate
8	Adequate furniture (chairs, desks, boards) in classrooms makes the students feel comfortable for learning towards enhance academic performance.	17 13.9	25 20.5	32 26.2%	48 39.3	2.13	Low
Grand Mean						2.70	

Source: Fieldwork 2024

Table 1 reveals the available facilities in private secondary in Ondo State with the grand mean of 2.70 against the criterion mean 2.50, this indicates that the level of school facilities is moderate. The teachers indicated that Library facilities provides a conducive environment for reading, and researching, thus, improving students' performance ($\bar{x}=2.98$), Students' academic performance becomes heighten when they are taught with appropriate laboratory facilities ($\bar{x}=2.76$), and Availability of clean blackboards or whiteboards aids students note taking and memorization for better academic performance ($\bar{x}=2.39$).

Research Question 2: What is the level of motivation in private secondary school in Ondo State?

Table 2: The Level of Motivation in Private Secondary School in Ondo State

S/N	Staff Motivation	VH%	MH%	H%	L%	Mean	Decision
9	The staff salary is being paid as at when due	14 11.5	32 26.2	51 41.8	25 20.5	3.08	High
10	The increment of staff salary in due time motivates them to put in their best in order to ensure that students' academic performance improves	28 23	35 28.7	22 18	39 32.3	3.06	High
11	Recognizing and appreciating of staff increases the teachers' commitment to improving the students' academic performance	51 41.8	32 26.2	28 23	11 9	2.48	Low
12	Appreciate of staff for the good deeds with reward apart from the salary	40 32.8	52 42.6	28 23	2 1.6	2.34	Low
13	Good conditions of workplace make staff go the extra mile in helping the students do well academically	14 11.5	26 21.3	51 41.8	31 25.4	2.29	Low
14	Equipping staff with resources that motivate them to work effectively enhances students' academic performance.	11 9	31 25.4	56 45.9	24 19.7	2.22	Low
Grand Mean						2.58	

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 reveals that the level of staff motivation is moderate. The grand mean is 2.58 against criterion mean of 2.50. The staff salary is being paid as at when due ($\bar{x}=3.08$), The increment of staff salary in due time motivates them to put in their best in order to ensure that students' academic performance improves ($\bar{x}=3.06$), and Recognizing and appreciating of staff contributions increases the teachers' commitment to improving the students' academic performance ($\bar{x}=2.48$)

Research Question 3: What is the level of school administration in private secondary school in Ondo State?

Table 3: The level of School Administration in Private Secondary School in Ondo State

S/N	School Administration	VH %	MH %	H %	L%	Mean	Decision
15	Principals' instructional supervision makes staff to put in their best, thus lead to positive academic performance of the students	31 25.4	46 37.7	34 27.9	11 9	3.10	High
16	The availability of qualified teachers in the school increases students moral for learning, hence, enhance students' academic performance	60 49.2	26 21.3	29 23.8	7 5.7	3.03	High
17	The principal's routine classroom and offices visitation improve staff' delivery of instruction	51 41.8	32 26.2	25 20.5	14 11.5	2.91	Moderate
18	Payment of staff salary as at when due plays some roles to play on students' academic performance	25 20.5	51 41.8	32 26.2	14 11.5	2.84	Moderate
19	The principal's supervision of staff activities helps to reduce staff deviation from the core task	26 21.3	60 49.2	29 23.8	7 5.7	2.79	Moderate
20	The school administration encourages teacher collaboration and professional development opportunities focused on improving student academic performance	32 26.2	51 41.8	14 11.5	25 20.5	2.76	Moderate
Grand Mean						2.92	

Source: Fieldwork 2024

Table 3 shows grand mean of 2.92 against criterion mean of 2.50 which indicate that the level of school administration is moderate. The teachers indicates that principals’ instructional supervision makes staff to put in their best, thus lead to positive academic performance of the students ($\bar{x}=2.91$), The principal’s supervision of staff activities helps to reduce staff deviation from the core task. ($\bar{x}=2.79$), and the school administration encourages teacher collaboration and professional development opportunities focused on improving student academic performance ($\bar{x}=2.76$).

Research Question 4: What are the students’ academic performance in private secondary schools in Ondo State?

Table 4: The inventory on students’ academic performance in WASSCE 2019/2020, 2020/2021, and 2021/2022 session

Academic session	No. of candidates registered	No. of candidates with 5 credits including English & mathematics	No. of candidates with 5 credits including either English or mathematics	No. of candidates with 5 credits without English & mathematics	No. of candidates with less than 5 credits
2020/2021	983	636	190	101	56
2021/2022	1,016	661	168	122	65
2022/2023	1,098	710	189	123	76

The Table 4 shows the level of students’ academic performance in private secondary schools in Ondo State based on the percentages of students’ numbers of credits in WASSCE in 2020/2021, 2021/2022, and 2022/2023 session. The number of candidates registered in the three sessions are (983, 1,016, 1,098) respectively; the number of candidates with 5 credits including English and mathematics 636; 661; and 710 respectively. The number of candidates with 5 credits including either English or mathematics for the three sessions are 190; 168; and 189 respectively. Likewise, the number of candidates with 5 credits without English & mathematics are 101, 122, and 123, respectively; the number of candidates with less than 5 credits 56; 65; and 76 respectively. With the results analyzed above, there is no doubt that the level of academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State is high.

Testing of the Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of school factors on academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State.

Table 5: The influence of all the management factors) on academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State

Variables	Coefficient			T	Sig.	R	R ²	F
	Unstandardized		Standardized					
	B	Std. Error	Beta					
(constants)	.182	.076		2.391	.018			
School Facilities	-.378	.085	-.374	-4.447	.000	0.967	0.935	4.606
Staff Motivation	.941	.066	1.015	14.364	.000			
School Administration	.369	.056	.344	6.543	.000			

P < 0.05

The results of multiple regression coefficients shown in Table 5 revealed that at 95% confidence level, a unit change in school facilities, staff motivation, and school administration will lead to standardized coefficient of 0.085, 0.066, and 0.056 which are all greater than 0.05 given that all other factors are held constant. Based on this result, the null hypothesis one (H01) which states that there is no significant relationship between all the management factors and academic performance of student in private secondary school in Ondo State is rejected. This means that there is significant relationship between all the management factors and academic performance of student in private secondary school in Ondo State. The individual contribution of each component of school factors is also shown on the table. Staff motivation was the best predictors of school factors, followed by school administration and the least was school facilities.

Discussion of the Findings

The study found in research question 1 that the level of school facilities is high. This indicates that the available school facilities enable students to have good academic performance. The library facilities provide a conducive environment for reading, and researching, thus, improving students' performance, Laboratory facilities enable students understand the scientific interaction around them thereby improving their retention, and other physical facilities such as toilet, playground, and eatery, among others make school environment lively and interesting for both students and teachers.

Similarly, research question 2 reveals that the level of staff motivation is high. staff motivation such as the staff salary being paid as at when due, good conditions of workplace make staff go the extra mile in helping the students to do well academically, and recognizing and appreciating of staff increases the teachers' commitment to improving the students' academic performance. The research question 3 also indicate that the level of school administration is high. school administration reveals that the principals' instructional supervision makes staff to put in their best, thus lead to positive academic performance of the students, the principal's supervision of staff activities helps to reduce staff deviation from the core task, and the availability of qualified teachers in the school increases students moral for learning, hence, enhance students' academic performance.

There is a link between the findings of this study and other several studies on the impact of management factors (school facilities, staff development, and school administration) on academic performance of students both in public and private secondary schools. Ajayi, and Ogunlaja (2021) investigated managerial factors, teacher job performance and secondary school effectiveness in Southwest, Nigeria. The findings show that there was significant relationship between managerial factors and secondary school effectiveness. Leithwood and Jantzi, (2015) research reveals that there is a great deal of evidence indicating that school management has a big impact on academic attainment. Similarly, Igbino and Marvelous (2015), find that management effectiveness is crucial in the school system, especially in the secondary schools where students expect for great achievement as prepare for higher education.

The research question 4 on the level of academic performance of students in private secondary school in Ondo State found that the level of academic performance of students is high. The study through the inventory on students' academic performance in WASSCE 2019/2020, 2020/2021, and 2021/2022 session. found further that the level of students' academic performance in private secondary schools in Ondo State based on the percentages of students' numbers of credits is high. The number of candidates registered in the three sessions are (983, 1,016, 1,098) respectively and the number of candidates with 5 credits including English and mathematics 636 (64.70%), 661 (65.06%), 710 (64.66%) respectively. There is also an agreement between the finding of this study and that of a comparative study conducted by Iddi (2016) on academic performance among public and private junior high schools. The findings show that, public schools display high poor outcomes from the external examinations than

the private schools. This means that the academic performance of students in private secondary school is always high in external examinations.

The hypothesis one tested in this study found that school factors (school facilities, staff motivation, and school administration) have a positive significant influence on academic performance of students in private secondary school in Akure, in Ondo State. This means that the academic performance of students can be enhanced if the school are well-managed with provision of some key factors. This is similar to a study by Kemenanabo, (2019) that investigated the perceived influence of some management factors on students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The results showed that all the management factors such as payment of staff, provision of physical facilities and staff motivation influence students' academic performance in senior secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent.

Conclusion

Academic performance of students is a critical issue in educational system. To ensure high student's academic performance in any educational institution, effective school factors is required. The study found that the level of the school factors in private secondary school in Ondo State is high.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Private schools in Ondo State should endeavor to make the school facilities available to enhance the academic performance of their students.
2. Both teaching and no-teaching staff should be motivated promptly and regularly to enhance their job performance, hence influence the academic performance of students.
3. There should be effective school administration in private secondary schools to impact on the academic performance of the students
4. Private secondary schools should always see that school factors (school facilities, staff motivation, and school administration) are properly considered and provided to improve the academic performance of the students

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